

Precarity's Hidden Toll: The Less Frequently Discussed Factors that Influence Researcher Mental Health

Tijana Milosevic and Darragh McCashin
Dublin City University

Precarious contracts appear to be the norm in the academic sector and are understood as a factor that adversely contributes to poor mental health in research and academic staff (McKay et al., 2008; Nititham, 2022). Bullying or mobbing are wide-spread issues in academia (Mazzone et al., 2022), and staff on precarious contracts are especially susceptible to being targeted; yet few of those who are affected and who witness such behaviors are able to report and stand up for themselves for the fear of negative impact on their careers. This is especially the case with early career scholars who have not yet established themselves or who do not have tenured contracts.

Bullying and incivility

There is a growing awareness of vulnerability of researchers and academics who are on short-term contracts to be exposed to actions and behaviors that may not always meet the criteria of bullying (such as intentionality and repetition); or which, for a lack of evidence, may be difficult to classify as bullying but are hurtful nonetheless, or that can otherwise contribute to burnout. For example, occasional incivilities which make one feel unwanted in an academic environment; or exclusion-based behaviors which are difficult to document (Heffernan & Bosetti, 2021; Hodgins & McNamara, 2019). There are many ways in which one can express hostility, and these can be very subtle, at the level of inter-personal exchanges that are hardly observable to those who are not targeted; and which can contribute to the person who is in a vulnerable position contract-wise to feel undervalued, unwelcome and which negatively affect their mental health in the long run.

These hostile behaviors can be difficult to provide evidence for, and an early career researcher who is heavily dependent on their mentor or supervisor will be particularly reluctant to bring anything up to the department. This is especially the case if the mentor/supervisor is an established well-networked scholar who regularly brings heavily cited publications and funding to the institution—the institution will be reluctant to intervene (see also Täuber, S., & Mahmoudi, 2022). These topics are difficult to research even when anonymity is guaranteed, since few, if anyone, is willing to put their professional relationships or even their own career on the line, especially for someone else.

The subtle ways in which precarious contracts can contribute to burnout also appear to be less frequently discussed (for some accounts and approaches to research and analyses see: Albayrak-Aydemir & Gleibs, 2023; Nititham, 2023). Researchers who are on successive short-term contracts are in a position where they need to prove themselves time and time again, and to many different supervisors/managers. Ensuring that the supervisor is *always* happy may entail the expectation of being available all the time, including for evening, late night and weekend requests. Such expectation of being available all the time and always delivering an excellent performance no matter what one is tasked with, can lead to neglecting one's own career goals; and can contribute to burn out. Once such worker actually suffers from burn out, it is more difficult to think clearly, let alone have novel ideas and a significant academic contribution.

Round table discussion

Goals of the proposed roundtable

- To outline a narrative review of the research regarding the connection between precarity and bullying, and its association with researcher mental health
- To facilitate a safe discussion using Chatham House Rules on participant experiences of these issues to inform ongoing research into anti-bullying approaches

References

Albayrak-Aydemir, N., & Gleibs, I. H. (2023). A social-psychological examination of academic precarity as an organizational practice and subjective experience. *British Journal of Social Psychology, 62*, 95-110.

Heffernan, T., & Bosetti, L. (2021). Incivility: The new type of bullying in higher education. *Cambridge Journal of Education, 51*(5), 641-652.

Hodgins, M., & McNamara, P. M. (2019). An enlightened environment? Workplace bullying and incivility in Irish higher education. *Sage open, 9*(4), 2158244019894278.

McKay, R., Arnold, D. H., Fratzl, J., & Thomas, R. (2008). Workplace bullying in academia: A Canadian study. *Employee responsibilities and rights Journal, 20*, 77-100.

Mazzone, A., Jones, E., Freney, Y., & O'Higgins Norman, J. (2022). *Report on the National Survey of Staff Experiences of Bullying in Higher Education Institutions*. DCU Anti-Bullying Centre. Retrieved from: https://antibullyingcentre.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/HEI_report_long_version.pdf

Nititham, D. S. (2022). Positionalities of Precarity: An Autoethnography of "Making It" in the Neoliberal Academy. *Journal of Autoethnography, 3*(1), 38-56.

Täuber, S., & Mahmoudi, M. (2022). How bullying becomes a career tool. *Nature human behaviour, 6*(4), 475-475.